

Density and viscosity of binary mixtures of methyl ethanoate with aromatic hydrocarbons at 298.15 K vis-a-vis molecular interactions

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The density and viscosity data of binary mixtures of methyl ethanoate +benzene, +toluene and +*o*-, +*m*- and +*p*-xylenes have been measured at 298.15 K. Excess volumes (V^E) have been calculated. The molecular interactions existing between the components are discussed. The results are used to justify theoretically the validity of several viscosity models.

Many physical techniques have so far been employed to study the molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures. But no method alone gives a complete understanding of the nature of intermolecular behaviour. Particularly, both IR and NMR spectroscopies, generally employed for these purposes, present least information about the reciprocal structures of neighbouring solvent molecules. This fact is very useful for understanding of solution physical properties, viz. stoichiometry, size, nature and configuration of species formed.

In continuation of our earlier study¹ on binary mixtures, we now report the density and viscosity data for the mixtures of methyl ethanoate with aromatic hydrocarbons at 298.15 K. Methyl ethanoate is the most representative solvent of ester group. It is a polar, electron-deficient aprotic solvent whereas the aromatic hydrocarbons are non-polar liquids. The experimental results are investigated theoretically for the validity of several viscosity models over the entire mole fraction range. The values of excess molar volume (V^E) have been predicted. The main aim of the study is to correlate the data with the nature and type of interactions between mixing components.

Results and Discussion

The density and viscosity data as a function of mole fraction (X_1) of methyl ethanoate (1) + aromatic hydrocarbon (2) mixtures at 298.15 ± 0.1 K are reported in Table 1. The observed excess molar volumes of mixing (V^E) were calculated from these density values. The V^E values were found to be positive for all the mixtures, indicating the existence of weak interactions² of the dipole-induced dipole type³ on account of the large difference between the dipole moments of moderately polar methyl ethanoate and non-polar aromatic hydrocarbons. The plots of V^E vs X_1 (Fig. 1) show that maxima occur around the middle of the mole fraction range, confirming the maximum specific interactions at equimolar compositions. This interaction strength varies in

the order, *o*-xylene < *p*-xylene < toluene < *m*-xylene < benzene, which is attributed to cumulative effect of two factors^{2,3}, i.e. (i) the specific interactions of the electron donor-acceptor type between the vacant $2p$ level of the oxygen atom in carbonyl group of methyl ethanoate and $n\pi$ -electron cloud of the aromatic hydrocarbon where the latter behaves as an electron donor, and (ii) the disruption in the orientation order of the two components.

The electron-donating power of benzene will increase with the introduction of a methyl group in the ring. Consequently, the electron donor-acceptor interactions⁴ will also exceed and the V^E values for the toluene mixtures would be less than those of benzene mixtures. Our experimental results support this conjecture. The addition of two methyl groups in benzene ring, alike xylenes, further exceeds the electron-donating capacity but at the same instant, there is steric repulsion between the methyl ethanoate molecules and the two bulky methyl groups, which hinders their proper orientation. The position of methyl groups in *m*-xylene is such that steric repulsion is maximum. That is why V^E values for the *m*-xylene mixtures are higher than those of *o*- and *p*-xylene mixtures and show the weakest interactions with component 1.

The polynomial function of the Redlich-Kister three parameter equation⁵ of the type

$$V_{\text{cal}}^E = x_1 x_2 \left[\sum_{i=0}^k A_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \right] \quad (1)$$

was fitted to each set of results to compute the values of the coefficients A_i (Table 2) by the least-squares method⁶. The coefficients A_i are then used to evaluate V_{cal}^E values by eqn. (1). The standard deviation⁷ $\sigma(V^E)$ (Table 2) is defined by the equation,

$$\sigma(V^E) = \left[\sum (V_{\text{obs}}^E - V_{\text{cal}}^E)^2 / (n - p) \right]^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) for methyl ethanoate + aromatic hydrocarbons at 298.15 K

X_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	η m Pa s	X_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	η mPa s
Methyl ethanoate (1) + benzene (2)			Methyl ethanoate (1) + toluene (2)		
0.0000	0.8794	0.603	0.0000	0.8623	0.552
0.1095	0.8827	0.543	0.1289	0.8678	0.497
0.2167	0.8862	0.496	0.2497	0.8733	0.446
0.3217	0.8898	0.456	0.3633	0.8788	0.403
0.4246	0.8936	0.420	0.4702	0.8842	0.377
0.5253	0.8976	0.392	0.5711	0.8904	0.372
0.6241	0.9024	0.382	0.6663	0.8968	0.369
0.7208	0.9073	0.374	0.7565	0.9032	0.368
0.8157	0.9124	0.370	0.8419	0.9097	0.368
0.9008	0.9176	0.367	0.9230	0.9163	0.367
1.0000	0.9230	0.366	1.0000	0.9230	0.366
Methyl ethanoate (1) + <i>o</i> -xylene (2)			Methyl ethanoate (1) + <i>m</i> -xylene (2)		
0.0000	0.8744	0.754	0.0000	0.8597	0.616
0.1439	0.8788	0.666	0.1460	0.8653	0.543
0.2744	0.8832	0.595	0.2778	0.8709	0.485
0.3933	0.8876	0.537	0.3974	0.8765	0.439
0.5021	0.8921	0.489	0.5064	0.8824	0.405
0.6020	0.8971	0.459	0.6061	0.8889	0.391
0.6941	0.9022	0.436	0.6977	0.8955	0.382
0.7792	0.9073	0.414	0.7821	0.9023	0.374
0.8582	0.9125	0.394	0.8602	0.9091	0.369
0.9316	0.9177	0.379	0.9326	0.9160	0.366
1.0000	0.9230	0.366	1.0000	0.9230	0.366
Methyl ethanoate (1) + <i>p</i> -xylene (2)					
0.0000	0.8558	0.614			
0.1466	0.8620	0.560			
0.2787	0.8683	0.517			
0.3985	0.8754	0.480			
0.5075	0.8807	0.448			
0.6072	0.8876	0.430			
0.6986	0.8946	0.413			
0.7829	0.9016	0.399			
0.8608	0.9087	0.386			
0.9329	0.9158	0.375			
1.0000	0.9230	0.366			

where n is the number of data points and p the number of coefficients. The optimum number of coefficients A_i is ascertained from an examination of the variation of the standard deviation $\sigma(V^E)$ with k . The standard errors in all the cases are less than 0.63%, except for the benzene mixture in which the error is 4.9%.

$$\eta = x_1\phi_1\eta_1 + x_2\phi_2\eta_2 + 2(x_1x_2\phi_1\phi_2)^{0.5} T_{12} \quad (3)$$

Tamura-Kurata⁸ proposed the above viscosity model for the

Fig. 1. Excess molar volume (V^E) at 298.15 K of methyl ethanoate (1) + aromatic hydrocarbons (2) : (○) benzene, (Δ) toluene, (●) *o*-xylene, (▲) *m*-xylene, (◊) *p*-xylene.

Table 2. Coefficients A_i and standard deviation $\sigma(V^E)$ for the representation of excess functions of methyl ethanoate + aromatic hydrocarbons at 298.15 K

Hydrocarbon	A_0	A_1	A_2	$\sigma(V^E)$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Benzene	1.3069	0.1017	-1.1322	0.0163
Toluene	0.9801	-0.4224	0.1191	0.0015
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.8087	-0.4247	0.1570	0.0003
<i>m</i> -Xylene	1.2079	-0.4341	0.1452	0.0012
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.9082	-0.5419	0.3080	0.0010

binary mixtures where ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the volume fractions and T_{12} is the interaction parameter. The T_{12} values (Table 3), found to be positive, support the existence of weak interactions. At equimolar fraction, T_{12} values and hence the strength of interaction varies in the order : *p*-xylene > *o*-xylene > *m*-xylene > toluene > benzene. The results are in accordance with the electron-donating power of the hydrocarbons^{2,9}.

The interaction parameter, H_{12} values were calculated using the following viscosity model proposed by Hind *et al.*¹⁰,

$$\eta = x_1^2\eta_1 + x_2^2\eta_2 + 2x_1x_2H_{12} \quad (4)$$

The H_{12} values (Table 3) are also found to be positive for all the mixtures and almost resemble with the T_{12} values. These values support the existence of dispersion forces³ followed by weak interactions and indicate a similar trend as discussed earlier.

McAllister¹¹ proposed the following equation,

$$\ln \eta = x_1^3 \ln \eta_1 + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln Z_{12} + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln Z_{21} + x_2^3 \ln \eta_2 - \ln(x_1 + x_2M_2/M_1) + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln[(2 + M_2/M_1)/3] + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln[(1 + 2(M_2/M_1)/3) + x_2^3 \ln(M_2/M_1) \quad (5)$$

Table 3. Values of interaction parameters T_{12} and H_{12} at 298.15 K

X_1	Φ_1	T_{12}	H_{12}	X_1	Φ_1	T_{12}	H_{12}
Methyl ethanoate + benzene				Methyl ethanoate + toluene			
0.0000	0.0	–	–	0.0000	0.0	–	–
0.1095	0.1	0.2959	0.3085	0.1289	0.1	0.2957	0.3205
0.2167	0.2	0.3101	0.3204	0.2497	0.2	0.2798	0.3013
0.3217	0.3	0.3140	0.3225	0.3633	0.3	0.2660	0.2833
0.4246	0.4	0.3095	0.3164	0.4702	0.4	0.2919	0.3039
0.5253	0.5	0.2849	0.3001	0.5711	0.5	0.3013	0.3084
0.6241	0.6	0.3250	0.3286	0.6663	0.6	0.3229	0.3265
0.7208	0.7	0.3379	0.3402	0.7565	0.7	0.3405	0.3417
0.8157	0.8	0.3510	0.3523	0.8419	0.8	0.3551	0.3546
0.9088	0.9	0.3599	0.3603	0.9230	0.9	0.3639	0.3618
1.0000	1.0	–	–	1.0000	1.0	–	–
Methyl ethanoate + <i>o</i> -xylene				Methyl ethanoate + <i>m</i> -xylene			
0.0000	0.0	–	–	0.0000	0.0	–	–
0.7439	0.1	0.3839	0.4276	0.2778	0.1	–	–
0.3933	0.2	0.3870	0.4243	0.3974	0.2	0.3007	0.3275
0.5021	0.3	0.3893	0.4205	0.5064	0.3	0.3022	0.3214
0.6020	0.4	0.4065	0.4322	0.6061	0.4	0.3255	0.3377
0.6941	0.5	0.4236	0.4452	0.6977	0.5	0.3416	0.3483
0.7792	0.6	0.4333	0.4514	0.7821	0.6	0.3520	0.3541
0.8582	0.7	0.4356	0.4499	0.8602	0.7	0.3130	0.3564
0.9316	0.8	0.4418	0.4533	0.9326	0.8	0.3658	0.3599
0.7545	0.9	0.4215	0.4431	0.8635	0.9	0.3426	0.3463
1.0000	1.0	–	–	1.0000	1.0	–	–
Methyl ethanoate + <i>p</i> -xylene							
0.0000	0.0	–	–				
0.1466	0.1	0.3902	0.4186				
0.2787	0.2	0.3954	0.4021				
0.3985	0.3	0.3967	0.4173				
0.5075	0.4	0.3932	0.4104				
0.6072	0.5	0.4062	0.4201				
0.6987	0.6	0.4135	0.4249				
0.7829	0.7	0.4187	0.4280				
0.8608	0.8	0.4234	0.4310				
0.9329	0.9	0.4239	0.4293				
1.0000	1.0	–	–				

for the viscosity of binary mixtures, where Z_{12} and Z_{21} are the interaction parameters of components 1 and 2, respectively. The values of Z_{12} and Z_{21} evaluated in the volume fraction range² 0.4–0.6 of methyl ethanoate using the least-squares method, are positive (Table 4). The interaction parameter, Z_{12} values vary in the order: *o*-xylene > *p*-xylene > toluene > *m*-xylene > benzene, which also reflects a trend similar to the earlier study².

Table 4. Values of McAllister parameters (Z_{12} , Z_{21}) and Heric and Brewer parameters (a , b , c) at 298.15 K

System	Z_{12}	Z_{21}	$10^2 a$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$10^2 b$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$10^2 c$ cm ² s ⁻¹
Methyl ethanoate +					
Benzene	0.3467	0.4167	-0.3938	0.0079	0.6824
Toluene	0.3840	0.3267	-0.3789	0.2971	-0.1604
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.4503	0.5159	-0.3197	0.1189	0.0698
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0.3813	0.3951	-0.3874	0.2256	-0.1409
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.4265	0.4657	-0.1848	0.1435	-0.1329

Heric and Brewer¹² suggested the following viscosity model,

$$\lambda = x_1\lambda_1 + x_2\lambda_2 + x_1x_2 [a + b(x_1 - x_2) + c(x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (6)$$

for the kinematic viscosity ($\lambda = \eta/\rho$) of binary mixtures, where λ_1 and λ_2 are kinematic viscosities of components 1 and 2, respectively. The values of parameters a , b and c were evaluated in the volume fraction range² 0.4–0.6 of methyl ethanoate using the least-squares method. The values of parameter a are negative for all mixtures (Table 4). The gradation in the values of parameter a , viz. *p*-xylene > *o*-xylene > toluene > *m*-xylene > benzene, reflects a trend similar to the previous models. However, no regular gradation is shown by the parameters b and c . The analysis suggests that the McAllister¹¹ model fits the data better than that of Heric and Brewer¹².

Experimental

Methyl ethanoate, benzene, toluene and *o*-, *m*-, *p*-xylenes were purified according to the standard procedures^{13,14}. Their purities were checked by density determination dilatometrically¹⁵ at 298.15 ± 0.1 K which almost agreed within the accuracy of ± 1 × 10⁻⁴ g cm⁻³ with the available literature^{16,17} values. All the solutions were prepared volumetrically¹⁸ in stoppered bottles. The method of preparation of the binary mixtures and other experimental details of the measurements of density and viscosity were the same as reported earlier¹. The experimental values were in close agreement with the literature values^{16,17}. The reproducibility of the results was better than ±0.5%.

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